

Calculation and comparison of mooring forces on a single point moored buoy in an aquaculture system located in the German North Sea

Bachelor Thesis

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Kurzfassung

In dieser Bachelorarbeit werden die Verankerungskräfte von vier verschiedene Bojen untersucht (Boje 1-4). Die Bojen sind dabei mittels Einzelpunktverankerung innerhalb eines Aquakultur-Systems bei der Forschungsplattform FINO3 in der deutschen Nordsee befestigt. Eine statistische Analyse von standortspezifischen Umweltdaten, einschließlich Wind-, Strömungs- und Wellenparametern, wurde durchgeführt, um 50-jährige Extrembedingungen zu definieren. Anhand dieser Daten wurde ein vereinfachtes numerisches Modell entwickelt, das die Bojendynamik und die Elastizität der Verankerungsleinen einbezieht.

Mit Hilfe einer Time-Domain Simulation wurden die Bojenbewegung und die damit verbundenen Kräfte für drei verschiedene Seezuständen (Seezustand 1-3) berechnet, die durch unterschiedliche Wellenenergiespektren dargestellt wurden. Seezustand 3 wurde aufgrund der hohen resultierenden Kräfte als der einflussreichste identifiziert. In Seezustand 3 wies die Boje 1 die geringsten maximalen Verankerungskräfte auf, während die Boje 3 das beste Kraft/Liter-Auftriebsverhältnis aufwies. Die Ergebnisse unterstreichen die entscheidende Rolle der dynamischen Modellierung bei der Erfassung extremer Belastungsszenarien und liefern Informationen für die Auswahl von Bojen und Verankerungsleinen für Offshore-Aquakulturanwendungen.

Zukünftige Arbeiten könnten das Modell verfeinern, indem beispielsweise dreidimensionale Bojenbewegungen, Rotationseffekte und komplexere Umweltinteraktionen einbezogen werden. Die Studie schafft eine Grundlage für die Verbesserung der Zuverlässigkeit und Sicherheit von Offshore-Aquakulturanlagen.

Abstract

This bachelor thesis investigates the mooring forces acting on four different single-point moored buoys (Buoy 1-4) within an aquaculture system located at the research platform FINO3 in the German North Sea. Statistical analysis of site-specific environmental data, including wind, current, and wave parameters, was conducted to define 50-year extreme conditions. With these data, a simplified numerical model incorporating buoy dynamics and mooring line elasticity was developed.

A time-domain simulation approach was used to calculate buoy motion and associated forces for three distinct sea states, represented by varied wave energy spectra (sea state 1-3). Sea state 3 was identified as the most influential because of the high resulting forces. In sea state 3 the Buoy 1 exhibited the lowest maximum mooring forces, while the Buoy 3 had the best force per liter buoyancy ratio. The findings emphasize the critical role of dynamic modelling in capturing extreme load scenarios and inform buoy selection and mooring line design for offshore aquaculture applications.

Future work could refine the model, for instance by incorporating three-dimensional buoy motion, rotational effects, and more complex environmental interactions. The study lays a foundation for improving the reliability and safety of offshore aquaculture systems.

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List of Abbreviations

EVA	extreme value analysis
COP	Copernicus
BM	block maxima
POT	peaks over threshold
GPD	generalized Pareto distribution
MLE	maximum likelihood estimation
PM	Pierson-Moskowitz
JONSWAP	Joint North Sea Wave Project
IFORM	inverse first order reliability method
SWL	still water line

List of Symbols

A Relevant cross-sectional area [m^2].

C_t Mooring line spring constant [N/m].

C_{dh} Horizontal hydrodynamic drag coefficient.

C_{dv} Vertical hydrodynamic drag coefficient.

C_{mh} Horizontal hydrodynamic added mass coefficient.

C_{mv} Vertical hydrodynamic added mass coefficient.

C_{wc} Horizontal Drag coefficient for Current.

C_{ww} Horizontal Drag coefficient for Wind.

E Young's modulus [kN/m^2].

F Force [N].

H Wave height [m].

L Wave length [m].

$S(f)$ Energy density over frequency wave spectrum.

$S_h(f)$ Wave height over frequency wave spectrum.

T Wave period [s].

V Volume of body [m^3].

\dot{c} Acceleration [m/s^2].

\dot{u} Horizontal water particle acceleration [m/s^2].

\dot{v} Vertical water particle acceleration [m/s^2].

α_i Uniformly distributed random phase shift.

β JONSWAP scale factor [m^2/s^2].
 η Wave elevation [m].
 γ JONSWAP peakedness enhancement factor.
 ψ Wave steepness.
 ρ_A Density of Air [kg/m^3].
 ρ_W Density of Water [kg/m^3].
 σ_u Shape parameter for the generalized Pareto Distribution.
 θ Drought of the buoy [m].
 ξ Scale parameter for the generalized Pareto Distribution.
 a Wave amplitude [m].
 b Anchor point depth/ length of line while body is at rest [m].
 c Wave phase speed [m/s].
 f Wave frequency [Hz].
 h Water depth [m].
 k Wave number [1/m].
 m Mass [kg].
 s Length of the mooring line [m].
 t Time [s].
 u Horizontal water particle velocity [m/s].
 v Vertical water particle velocity [m/s].
 x Horizontal position coordinate of the buoy [m].
 z Vertical position coordinate of the buoy [m].

1 Introduction

Due to the growing utilization of European waters, the expansion of offshore wind energy on the open sea and increased environmental considerations, the need for intelligent multi-use strategies of marine areas is ever-increasing (CORDIS 2023). This raises the question of how the available ocean spaces can be used more efficiently and diversely.

A research group at the FuE-Zentrum FH-Kiel GmbH has been addressing this challenge since January 2020 in the EU Project UNITED and since June 2023 in the EU project ULTFARMS. Within these projects, the research group focuses on the design and operation of low-trophic aquaculture systems at the FINO3 research platform in the German North Sea (CORDIS 2023; ULTFARMS consortium n.d.). The main challenges for construction and operation at this location are the great distance from the coast and the harsh offshore weather conditions, which place a heavy load on all components (CORDIS 2023). Figure 1.1 shows the FINO3 and its location in the North Sea.

Figure 1.1: Position and photo of the FINO3 research platform in the German North Sea from Gryning and Floors (2019) and FINO (n.d.).

One of the aquaculture systems operated off FINO3 is a mussel farming net which is held at a defined water depth by several buoys. The system itself is held in place by anchors. At the time of this thesis, the buoys are connected to a submerged main tube via steel chains or polymer ropes. However, repeated failure of the connecting lines in the past, shows the need

for optimization or a full redesign of these lines. In this bachelor thesis, an initial calculation of the prevailing environmental conditions and the resulting forces on the buoyancy bodies will therefore be carried out. This is followed by a comparison of the behaviour and the mooring forces of four different types of buoys available in the project. The aim of this bachelor thesis is to accurately predict the buoy behaviours and to give guidance on buoy selection, in addition to providing a reproducible workflow for future installations in the running and future projects.

Firstly, the moored buoy is then modelled as a simplified two dimensional spring damper system. Then, environmental data from the FINO3 is used to determine the statistical extreme environmental conditions with the help of an extreme value analysis and an environmental contour plot. This will result in a 50-year wind and current speed, together with a range of possible significant wave height and peak wave period pairs. Three of the pairs are selected to calculate independent wave spectra in order to represent three possible irregular ocean surfaces.

Following the definition of the environmental conditions, the equations describing the transfer of forces from the environment to the buoy are defined. After all system properties are defined, the buoy movement and all acting forces are calculated via a numerical time domain solution in order to capture the dynamics of the system. This calculation is repeated for all four different buoys for three different wave spectra each. The results are then compared and evaluated.

2 Framework

In this chapter, the necessary framework for the calculations in the later chapters is introduced.

2.1 Model and Model Limitations

Real world problems have often to be reduced in complexity and assumptions have to be made in order to make calculation feasible and time efficient. This section explains the model constraints and assumptions made in this thesis.

2.1.1 Mussel System

The mussel system consists of a 40m long polymer tube with a net attached to it, on which mussels can grow. The tube is connected to two concrete anchor stones that, in turn, are attached to drag anchors to hold the system in place. The system is kept afloat in 7m water depth by several buoys that are connected to the tube through chains or rope, depending on the specific design. In the model for this thesis, the connection will be modelled as a 20 mm steel wire rope. The rope is chosen because it represents a middle ground between the mentioned steel chains and polyester ropes with a similar diameter as used before (19 mm-32 mm). The number of buoys also varies through the different iterations of the design, since the amount needed depends on the buoyancy provided by each individual one.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the mussel system deployed by the German ULTFARMS team around the research platform FINO3, located in the German North Sea, with measurements that show the general dimensions of each section. (Illustration provided by the FuE Zentrum FH-Kiel GmbH)

The weight of the system changes over time for several reasons. Firstly, the position of the system is relevant for the weight, as a larger excursion can lead to longer sections of chain leaving the ocean floor, adding to the suspended weight. Secondly, the growth of mussels and unwanted biofouling add to the mass over time. However, the change of mass over time is not accounted for in this thesis, and the weight of the components is added up to about, 2000 kg (weight in water). This will be used in the calculations of the baseline draught of the buoys.

The position of the connection between the mussel system and the mooring line of the buoys is treated as fixed. This follows the assumption that with a greater number of buoys keeping the system afloat, the position of the tube stays relatively consistent since the buoys are located at different positions of a travelling wave.

2.1.2 Buoys

In this section, the four different buoys and their corresponding relevant parameters that will be used for calculation are shown. Table 2.1 shows the general dimensions and shape of the buoys to give an overview.

Table 2.1: General dimensions of the different buoy types used in this study.

Buoy	Height [m]	Diameter/Side Length [m]	Buoyancy [l]	Schematic
Buoy 1	3.00	0.30	200	
Buoy 2	1.65	0.45	208	
Buoy 3	1.65	0.77x0.77	560	
Buoy 4	1.80	0.32	109	

Coefficients

There are six coefficients that influence the forces (chapter 2.3) acting on the different buoys. The hydrodynamic added mass and drag coefficients for the vertical (C_{mv} , C_{dv}) and horizontal (C_{mh} , C_{dh}) directions and the drag coefficients for the constant wind (C_{ww}) and current (C_{wc}) forces. In order to find accurate values for more complex shapes, model tests are generally needed and should additionally be calibrated with field data (DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V. 2013). However, since such tests or computational simulations to substitute are not in the scope of this thesis, simplified values from DNV AS (2019), Kurniawan (2013), Journée and Massie (2001) and Spektrum (1998) are chosen and shown in table 2.2. For the vertical wave forces, all buoys are treated as bullet shaped and to achieve a representation of the irregular sea the peak wave period T_p is used as the benchmark since it is associated with the significant wave height. For the horizontal movement, all buoys are treated as vertical, cylinders with a smooth surface. If severe fouling is to be observed at the site, this assumption might be changed to a rough surface to better represent the acting

forces. This goes for wave forces in addition to the wind and the current.

Table 2.2: Different buoy types with their corresponding coefficients.

Buoy	C_{mh}	C_{dh}	C_{mv}	C_{dv}	C_{ww}	C_{wc}
Buoy 1	1.00	0.65	0.085	0.002	0.35	1.2
Buoy 2	0.84	0.65	0.085	0.002	0.35	1.2
Buoy 3	0.76	0.65	0.120	0.020	0.35	1.2
Buoy 4	0.95	0.65	0.085	0.002	0.35	1.2

All the used values stem from fairly simple models with limited complexity and while there are several more complex models, these models also differ up to 30% in the resulting forces (Journée and Massie 2001). In the light of this, the necessary model simplifications and lack of test data, the calculations will be made with simple assumptions instead of a complex model with limited accuracy.

2.1.3 Model

The calculations focus only on one buoy that is connected to a single fixed point. This allows the problem to become a single body problem, which simplifies calculations and reduces calculation time greatly. Furthermore, the buoy movement is limited to only the x-z plane and no rotational moments from the forces in chapter 2.3 are considered. Wind, waves and current are treated as unidirectional in order to account for the worst possible scenario. As mentioned in chapter 2.2 the wind and current are treated as constant while the waves have an assigned spectrum. In this case, every buoy will be tested for the three different sea states discussed in section 2.2.3 with constant wind and current. The decline in wave force over the water depth will not be considered.

Since the buoy diameter is small compared to the wave length, the water level is treated as constant over the diameter of the buoy. The mooring line is treated as a spring that does not absorb bending or torsion moments and compression forces. The following figure 2.2 shows the schematic layout of the model.

Figure 2.2: Schematic of the buoy model used in the calculations. The buoy is connected to its anchor point via a spring-like line, with force arrows showing the general force distribution and directions.

2.2 Environmental Factors

For a floating buoy on the ocean, the environment is the governing factor to influence its loads and behaviour. Therefore, it is essential to identify and calculate the relevant environmental conditions. This chapter provides an overview of the acting wind speeds, current speeds and waves, detailing the process that has been used to acquire values for the three categories. For all categories, a so-called 50-year return period has been decided on for the design environment. This means, that the resulting winds, currents and waves all have a 1-in-50 chance to occur every year. All resulting graphs from this chapter can be found in appendix A.

2.2.1 Data Selection

To accurately predict the environment around the FINO3, measurement data from that location was used. For this thesis, the possible sources are either the INSITU measurements taken directly at the FINO3 (INSITU n.d.) or the data sets from Copernicus (COP) (Copernicus n.d.). The latter provides a longer time series (~ 40 years) than the INSITU data (~ 14 years) which would be advantageous since longer time series generally provide better accuracy for the statistical models such as extreme value analysis (EVA) that were used (Schmidt et al. 2014). However, the measurements from the two sources are not consistent, with Copernicus tending to underestimate for instance the wave height as can be seen in figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of INSITU and Copernicus (COP) significant wave height data at the FINO3 research platform, located in the German North Sea, between September 2013 and June 2014. The plot shows that INSITU measurements exceed simultaneous COP results by up to 40%.

This discrepancy in the measurements is a known issue (Naderi and Siadatmousavi 2023) without an easy to implement solution, especially since wave height and wavelength are so closely related that "correcting" one of the two parameters would undoubtedly have an impact on the reliability of the other one. For this reason, only the INSITU measurements will be used for the calculations in the following chapters, since the measurements taken at the site are deemed more reliable than the calculated COP data. One should however keep in mind that this shorter time frame might decrease the accuracy of any results.

The data is checked for seasonality to ensure an even distribution across the months of the year. Otherwise, a greater amount of values in, for example, the summer months could lead to an underestimation of the extreme values. For wind speed, the results are shown in figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Number of wind speed data points per month of the year. The data points are INSITU wind speed measurements taken every ten minutes at the research platform FINO3, located in the German North Sea, between 01.10.2013 until 30.09.2023.

2.2.2 Wind and Current

To predict a 50-year wind speed or current from limited amounts of past data, extrapolation with statistical methods is required (Dhanak and Xiros 2016). Here, we will use EVA and apply it to a 50-year return period regarding wind and current speed. Since the process is identical for both wind and current speed, only exemplary graphs for either wind or current are shown in this section.

The data for the current speed is measured at 10 m depth and the data for the wind speed at 61 m height. The EVA will be performed with the data points from these heights, however the wind speed will be corrected to 3m above surface height later. This will help to get a more realistic representation of current and wind speeds acting on the buoys.

Extreme Value Analysis

Extreme value analysis is build on the principle, that the extreme values of a data set follow a different distribution than the whole of the data. There are two main methods for EVA, the block maxima (BM) and the peaks over threshold (POT) method. This thesis, will focus on the POT method, since it is better fit for the smaller sample period of about thirteen years (Caires and Sterl 2005). To avoid splitting the winter period in two, the year will be defined as October to September in this exercise (Coles 2004). For the POT method, a threshold is defined, above which the values are treated as extremes. The threshold selection

is crucial in this method, since a value that is too low would mean that the “extremes” do not satisfy the EVA condition, and on the other hand a threshold that is too high would result in very few usable data points, which increases the variance greatly (Coles 2004). It is therefore a delicate balance to decide on a fitting threshold.

The common approach for this is the graphical threshold selection, which is prone to error and relies on personal experience and therefore introduces bias (Thompson et al. 2009). For that reason, in this thesis, the “Automated threshold selection methods for extreme wave analysis” (Thompson et al. 2009) will be employed via a python script to ensure reliable threshold selection. This method will be explained further in the section Automated Threshold Selection.

The mathematical background of the EVA methods assumes the independence of the used variables (Coles 2004). To ensure that all values are independent, and therefore e.g. not part of the same storm, a minimum cluster size of 48h between two consecutive extremes is defined (Caires and Sterl 2005). In addition to waves and wind, this has been applied to the current data, since the current at the ocean surface is influenced by storms as well (Perrie et al. 2003). This also eliminates the clustering of the tides. Figure 2.11 illustrates the definition of extremes above a set threshold and cluster size.

Figure 2.5: Illustration of extreme value selection using a $8.83 \frac{m}{s}$ threshold and a 24-hour cluster size. The wind speed data are INSITU measurements taken at the FINO3 research platform, located in the German North Sea, between October 2012 and September 2023.

After the peaks are defined, they are sorted in ascending order, plotting their probability against their magnitude (Dhanak and Xiros 2016). A generalized Pareto distribution (GPD)

is now fitted to the data by using the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) (Caires and Sterl 2005) as can be seen in figure 2.6. The occurrence probabilities can be translated to return periods and therefore, with a defined return period, a corresponding extreme value can be found.

Figure 2.6: Values for current speed measurements acquired in a peak over threshold method sorted in ascending order. The values are binned automatically, with the y-axis representing their combined probability density. A Generalized Pareto Distribution (red) is fitted to the values using the maximum likelihood estimation.

Extreme values outside the original data set, for example for a 50-year return period, can now be found by following the curve of the GPD. The following flowchart 2.7 shows how this procedure was done practically for the wind speed with the python package "pyextremes" (Bocharov 2023).

Figure 2.7: Flowchart depicting the processing steps done in python from raw INSITU wind speed data to a 50-year extreme wind speed value with the python package "pyextremes".

Automated Threshold Selection

The following text explains the automated threshold selection as suggested by Thompson et al. (2009). As mentioned above, a GPD is fitted to the extreme values using the MLE. The two parameters used to fit this distribution are the scale parameter ξ and the shape parameter σ_u . The parameters are now used to find a fitting threshold.

Let p_1, \dots, p_n be n suitable threshold candidates that are equally spaced and therefore $\hat{\xi}_{p_j}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{p_j}$ the parameters for each threshold p . As recommended by the authors of the method, $n = 100$, n_1 is set as the median and p_{100} the 98% quantile of the data (if there are less than 100 data points above the 98% quantile, p_{100} is to be set as the 100th data point in descending order).

While

$$\tau_{p_j} = \hat{\sigma}_{p_j} - \hat{\xi}_{p_j} p_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, \quad (2.1)$$

view the differences

$$\tau_{p_j} - \tau_{p_{j-1}} \quad j = 2, \dots, n, \quad (2.2)$$

which should follow a normal distribution if p is a suitable threshold. This is examined by applying the Pearson's Chi-square Test and checking for rejection of the null hypothesis.

If the null hypothesis is rejected the distribution is not normal, and we change $p = p_2$, remove $\tau_{p_2} - \tau_{p_1}$ from the set of differences and repeat the process. If the null hypothesis is not rejected, we consider this value of p as a fitting threshold and move on to the EVA.

In the case that none of the 100 selected p values lead to a suitable threshold, the method can not be applied and other methods such as the graphical approach have to be used. This however happens only rarely and not in the case of this thesis.

Wind and Current Results

Following the procedure described in this section, thresholds for the EVA were selected and subsequently 50-year values were defined in table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Thresholds and corresponding 50-year return period values for wind and current speeds.

Environmental Factor	Threshold	50-Year Speed
Wind	$8.83 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$	$35 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$
Current	$0.426 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$	$1.23 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$

It is worth noting that for the wind speed, the selected threshold equals the median of the data set and is therefore surprisingly low. However, even a threshold set about three times as high at $25 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$, only provided a small ($3 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$) increase in expected 50-year speed. Because of this, the value of $8.83 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ is deemed sensible.

2.2.3 Waves

In all the years of ocean engineering, many theories, models and terms have been coined to explain the behaviour of the ocean waves and to find a way to express this in simple mathematical terms. Because of this, a selection has been made to adequately represent the waves and their behaviour. In this section, the basic models and parameters that have been chosen to do the calculation in chapter 3 are explained.

The section begins with a fundamental explanation of ocean waves before it moves on to more complex models and the statistical methods used.

Wave Parameters

Wave parameters are the fundamental characteristics that are used to describe a wave. To describe the base form of an ocean wave fully, only three parameters are needed (Chakrabarti 2005; Dean and Dalrymple 2000).

1. wave period T , which is the time it takes a wave to complete a full swinging motion. This can be defined as the time between two wave crests to pass a particular point in succession (Chakrabarti 2005; Dean and Dalrymple 2000).
2. wave height H , which is the vertical distance between a wave crest and the following trough. If the wave is linear, this height equals twice the amplitude a (Chakrabarti 2005).
3. water depth h , this parameter is defined as the distance from the still water line (SWL) to the ocean floor. Since the z coordinate axis has its origin at the SWL, the bottom of the ocean will be at $z = -h$ (Dean and Dalrymple 2000).

These three main parameters can then be applied to calculate other parameters used in the context of ocean wave engineering. A few more important examples are:

- wavelength L , which is the distance between two successive identical points on the wave, e.g. the distance between two crests $L = \frac{g}{2\pi f}$ (Bergdahl and Kofoed 2015).
- frequency f , which is defined as $\frac{1}{T}$.
- phase speed c , which is calculated as $\frac{L}{T}$ and is the speed in which the wave crest propagates.
- wave elevation, η which is the instantaneous distance between wave and SWL for a single point.
- u , \dot{u} , v , and \dot{v} which are horizontal particle velocity and acceleration and vertical particle velocity and acceleration respectively.
- k is the wave number $k = \frac{2\pi}{L}$.

This leads to a possible description of a simple wave, as can be seen in figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Illustration of a simple water wave, showing the parameters: wave height H , amplitude a , wavelength L , water depth h , crest, and trough from Dean and Dalrymple (2000).

The equations describing the position, velocity and acceleration of a point on the wave according to Holthuijsen (2007) are

$$\eta = \frac{H}{2} \cos \omega t \quad (2.3)$$

$$u = \omega \frac{H \cosh kh}{2 \sinh kh} \sin \omega t \quad (2.4)$$

$$\dot{u} = \omega^2 \frac{H \cosh kh}{2 \sinh kh} \cos \omega t \quad (2.5)$$

$$v = \omega \frac{H}{2} \cos \omega t \quad (2.6)$$

$$\dot{v} = -\omega^2 \frac{H}{2} \sin \omega t \quad (2.7)$$

Linear Waves

As explained in McCormick (2010) and Holthuijsen (2007), the linear wave theory, also known as Airy wave theory, has been developed in the nineteenth century and treats waves as a simple sine form. It gives a good approximation of real wave behaviour for waves with a small wave steepness $\psi = H/L$. This theory treats the flow of water as irrotational and the water itself as inviscid, incompressible and homogenous. In addition, three boundary conditions are set.

- Kinematic Free-Surface Condition: The water surface is comprised of the same particles at all time.
- Dynamic Free-Surface Condition: The pressure at the surface is zero.
- Sea-Floor Condition: No particles can cross through the seafloor, resulting in a vertical velocity of 0 at that boundary.

In the case of this thesis, the assumption of linearity is made regardless of the wave steepness, since the calculation of anything but regular waves becomes much more complicated otherwise (Pecher and Kofoed 2017). Luckily, the theory has proven to be quite robust and to produce meaningful results even with steeper waves (Holthuijsen 2007). However, in consequence, this is still a potential error to keep in mind in the later calculation.

Regular Waves

In regular wave theory, waves are treated as constant in wavelength, amplitude and frequency (Letcher 2022). With the addition of linear wave theory, the waves are also following a sinusoidal shape (Letcher 2022). One way this theory is used in ocean engineering is by defining a design wave and assuming it to be regular. This design wave should be the highest wave the structure is expected to withstand (Chakrabarti 2005).

Irregular Waves and Wave Spectra

Real ocean waves are not regular and constant in amplitude and frequency but rather random or irregular in nature (Chakrabarti 2005). Because of this randomness, statistics have to be introduced (Chakrabarti 2005). Through the superposition of many regular wave components, an irregular wave can be created (Faltinsen 1993; Holthuijsen 2007). With infinitesimal steps between the wave frequencies used, this irregular wave can be fully displayed as a frequency spectrum as can be seen in figure 2.9 (Holthuijsen 2007; Ma et al. 2019). This is now a short term description of the sea where it is treated as stationary, which constitutes that only limited periods of time (≤ 10 h) are used (Faltinsen 1993).

This spectrum is often displayed with regard to the wave amplitudes or the energy density (Holthuijsen 2007; Ma et al. 2019).

Figure 2.9: Figure illustrating the relationship between regular wave components, irregular wave and wave spectrum taken from Dhanak and Xiros (2016).

The narrower the spectrum the closer it gets to a regular wave, this means that a spectrum only a single frequency wide is a regular wave (Holthuijsen 2007). The two most commonly used spectra are the Pierson-Moskowitz (PM) spectrum and the Joint North Sea Wave Project (JONSWAP) spectrum (Hasselmann et al. 1973). Both spectra can be seen in comparison in figure 2.10. The JONSWAP spectrum is a PM spectrum with an added peakedness enhancement factor and is defined by significant wave height H_s , peak wave energy period T_p and peakedness enhancement factor γ (Ma et al. 2019). Since JONSWAP was developed specifically for the North Sea, it will be used here.

Figure 2.10: Difference between a Pierson-Moskowitz and a JONSWAP spectral density spectrum for ocean waves. Both spectra are calculated with the same significant wave height. The figure is taken from Bergdahl and Fransson (2009).

The JONSWAP spectrum can then be calculated as

$$S(f) = \beta \cdot f^{-5} \exp \left[-\frac{5}{4} \left(\frac{f}{f_p} \right)^{-4} \right] \gamma \exp \left[-\frac{(f-f_p)^2}{2\sigma^2 f_p^2} \right] \quad (2.8)$$

where

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} \sigma_a = 0.07 & \text{if } f \leq f_p \\ \sigma_a = 0.09 & \text{if } f \geq f_p \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

and (Dhanak and Xiros 2016)

$$\beta = \frac{5}{16} H_s^2 f_p^2 \left(1.15 + 0.168\gamma - \frac{0.925}{1.909 + \gamma} \right)^{-1} \quad (2.10)$$

When no peakedness parameter γ is given, it may be calculated according to the DNV Position Mooring standard (DNV AS 2021).

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} = 5 & \text{if } \frac{T_p}{\sqrt{H_s}} \leq 3.6 \\ = e^{5.75 - 1.15 \cdot \frac{T_p}{\sqrt{H_s}}} & \text{if } 3.6 \leq \frac{T_p}{\sqrt{H_s}} < 5 \\ = 1.0 & \text{if } 5 \leq \frac{T_p}{\sqrt{H_s}} \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

In case of insufficient data, the peakedness factor can also be approximated as $\gamma = 3.3$ for

the North Sea (DNV AS 2021).

The JONSWAP spectrum is displayed as energy density over frequency but can also be converted to wave height over frequency (Journée and Massie 2001).

$$S_h(f) = 2 \cdot \sqrt{S(f)df} \quad (2.12)$$

This is useful because the wave force calculations in chapter 2.3 all rely on wave height.

Environmental Contour Plot

In order to define the relevant wave conditions for a 50-year period, an environmental contour plot is employed. The environmental contour plot differs from the EVA mentioned in section 2.2.2 mainly in the way that now the two sets of data (wave height and period) are not treated as independent any-more, but rather as pairs of two. The aim is therefore not to find a 50-year wave height but a 50-year pair of wave height and period.

Again, there are several methods to approach this problem, of which we will focus on the DNV recommended inverse first order reliability method (IFORM) (DNV AS 2019). The following paragraph explains the method as shown in Clarindo, Teixeira, and Guedes Soares (2021) and Kim (2020).

In order to use this method, the two sets of data must be assigned a distribution function. A 3-parameter Weibull distribution for the significant wave height H_s and a conditional log-normal distribution is used for the wave period T_p . This means that the distribution of T_p is directly connected to H_s . Both functions used with the IFORM, together with a specified return period, yield an environmental contour plot displayed in 2.11. All pairs of H_s and T_p that are on the red contour have the same probability and therefore return period.

Figure 2.11: Environmental contour plot for a return period of 50-years, drawn with the python module "virocon". All hypothetical data pairs that lay on the contour line have the same occurrence probability of 2% per year.

The following flow chart 2.12 explains how this process was done using the python module "virocon" (Haselsteiner et al. 2019).

Figure 2.12: Flowchart for the processing steps from raw INSITU measurements for significant wave height and peak wave period data to 50-year T_p/H_s pairs. The process is done using the python module "virocon" mainly following the steps recommended by Kim (2020).

The following graph 2.13 shows the spectra for three different H_s/T_p pairs that have been selected from the environmental contour plot in order to get a range of possible wave spectra. As all spectra are equally likely, the spectrum with the highest significant wave height has been chosen together with two arbitrary spectra that share a significant wave height but differ widely in peak wave period.

Figure 2.13: JONSWAP wave height spectra for 50-year sea states based on three different chosen H_s/T_p pairs with a 50-year return period each.

As can be seen, although all options are equally likely, the wave spectra vary widely in expected wave height and frequencies. This shows the need to test for different points on the contour line, as to not underestimate the relevance of certain frequencies.

In connection with the wind and current, these three wave spectra represent three different sea states and are therefore henceforth called sea state 1-3. Sea State 1: $H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s. Sea State 2: $H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s. Sea State 3: $H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s.

2.3 Relevant Buoy Forces

The forces acting on a body govern its movement and behaviour. Therefore, in this chapter the different forces acting on a buoy are listed and the governing equations that are used are shown and explained. This section deals with wave, wind/current and mooring line forces separately.

2.3.1 Wave Forces

This section shows the formulas used to calculate the wave forces on the buoy. The forces will be separated into horizontal and vertical forces that will ultimately act together on the buoy.

For the horizontal forces on a buoy, two forces will be considered. These forces are the mean wave drift force and the first order wave force (Pecher and Kofoed 2017).

Mean Wave Drift Force

Pecher and Kofoed (2017) explain how the mean wave drift force can be applied to a small body: For a regular wave with amplitude a hitting an immovable vertical wall with width D , a wave with the same amplitude will be reflected. A force will be exerted on the wall that equates to the difference in momentum between the incoming and reflected wave

$$F_d = I_{in} - I_{out} = \frac{\rho_w g a^2}{2} \cdot D \quad (2.13)$$

If repeated for every amplitude component of our spectrum, this can be used for irregular waves as well

$$F_d = \frac{1}{2} \rho_w g \sum_i \frac{1}{2} a_i^2 \cdot D \quad (2.14)$$

This is a very conservative approach since it assumes all the incoming waves to be reflected. For a smaller and floating body, however, not all the waves get reflected, since the body can move with the waves and radiate some of the waves' energy. Generally, only wavelengths smaller than about 5 times the diameter of the body get reflected at all. The shorter the waves, the more of their energy gets reflected.

Even with a conservative take that suggests that for all wavelengths below $5 \cdot D$, 100% of the wave energy gets reflected, all the wave components in the spectrum used in this calculation will be above that wavelength and the resulting force should therefore be small and negligible. This is because the highest frequency described in the used JONSWAP

spectra is about 0.25 Hz, and therefore the shortest wave length is about 25 m. Therefore, it is to be expected that any buoy with a diameter of less than 5 m is experiencing negligible mean wave drift forces. This is true for all the buoy types compared in this thesis, as can be seen in section 2.1.2.

First Order Wave Forces

For the second part of the horizontal wave forces, the Morison equation for slender bodies will be used. The Morison equation is an approximation that neglects effects such as the orbital motion of the water particles and vortex shedding for a simpler calculation. This approximation is possible because we are dealing with a slender structure that fulfils $\frac{\lambda}{D} > 5$ as mentioned above (American Bureau of Shipping July 2022; Chakrabarti 2005; DNV AS 2019). The Formula is made up of a part for the drag forces and a part for the inertia forces, which together approximate the wave force (Dean and Dalrymple 2000; Pecher and Kofoed 2017).

$$F_{Morison} = \rho_W V \dot{u} - m \ddot{x} + C_{mh} \rho_W V (\dot{u} - \ddot{x}) + \frac{1}{2} C_{dh} \rho_W A |u - \dot{x}| (u - \dot{x}) \quad (2.15)$$

- $F_{Morison}$ is the resulting Force
- ρ_W is the density of water
- V is the volume displaced by the body
- u and \dot{u} the horizontal water velocity and acceleration in the middle of the body
- m the body mass
- x , \dot{x} and \ddot{x} are the horizontal position, velocity and acceleration of the body
- C_{mh} is the added mass coefficient
- C_{dh} is the drag coefficient
- A the submerged cross-sectional area of the body perpendicular to the relative velocity

This version of the Morison equation follows the more precise relative velocity approach where, not, the speed of the buoy or the water but the relative speed and acceleration between those are considered. This means that these values can not be computed independently but in relation to each other, which increases the complexity in calculation (Journée and Massie

2001).

The vertical forces on the buoy can also be treated as two separately acting forces. The wave exciting forces which are the forces the moving wave exerts on a still body and the hydromechanical forces which are the forces induced by the motion of the body through still water (Journée and Massie 2001). These forces can be calculated independently and superposed afterwards (figure 2.14).

Figure 2.14: Superposition of the vertical wave forces of a free floating body as a force acting on a body moving in still water and a wave force acting on a fixed body. Figure from Journée and Massie (2001).

Wave Exciting Forces

For the wave exciting forces, the "Froude Krylov Force" is considered firstly for a regular wave.

$$F_{WaveV} = \zeta \cdot e^{-k\theta} \cdot (C_g - C_{mv} \cdot \omega^2) \cdot \cos \omega t - \zeta \cdot e^{-k\theta} \cdot (c_{dv}\omega) \cdot \sin \omega t \quad (2.16)$$

To adapt the equation for an irregular sea a few changes and compromises have to be made. Firstly, the wave number k gets replaced by an average wave number k_{av} that averages all wave numbers of frequencies in the spectrum. Secondly, the wave height parts $\zeta \cdot \cos \omega t$ and $\zeta \cdot \sin \omega t$ have to be changed to the superposed wave components as explained in 2.2.3. These components consist of sine and cosine waves, respectively. Lastly, the remaining radial frequency ω is set as the radial frequency of the spectrum's peak wave period.

$$F_{WaveV} = \zeta_{sin} \cdot e^{-k_{av}\theta} \cdot (C_g - C_{mv} \cdot \omega_{Tp}^2) - \zeta_{cos} \cdot e^{-k_{av}\theta} \cdot (c_{dv}\omega_{Tp}) \quad (2.17)$$

This leads to a relatively precise output that avoids recalculating the wave elevation and frequency during every step of calculating the wave forces. This means that the wave elevation can be calculated first and then be applied to the force equations instead of calculating the force for every wave component individually.

The comparison in figure 2.15 shows that the simplification made is viable, since the difference in resulting force can be considered small.

Figure 2.15: Output of the vertical "Froude Krylov Force" 2.16 and of a simplified equation 2.17 acting on a cylinder. The equation is simplified to allow for faster calculation in the time domain.

Hydrodynamic Forces

For the hydrodynamical forces, the movement of a buoy in still water is considered (Journée and Massie 2001).

$$F_H = (m + C_{mv}) \cdot \ddot{z} + C_{dv} \cdot \dot{z} + C_t \cdot z \quad (2.18)$$

- F_H is the resulting hydrodynamic force
- C_{mv} is the added mass coefficient
- C_{dv} is the drag coefficient
- C is the spring coefficient of the mooring line
- z is the position and subsequently \dot{z} and \ddot{z} are the speed and acceleration of the buoy in vertical direction

2.3.2 Wind and Current Forces

Wind and current forces are calculated through the standard formula for the flow resistance (Spektrum 1998)

$$F_{W/C} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v_{w/c}^2 A C_w \quad (2.19)$$

- $F_{W/C}$ is the resulting current or wind force
- ρ is the density of water (ρ_W) or air (ρ_A)
- $v_{W/C}$ is the current (v_C) or wind speed (v_W)
- A is the area of the cross-section of the buoy that is under or over the water line respectively
- C_w is the drag coefficient for water or air

The wind and current speed (from table 2.3) are treated as constant so that the change of force only comes from the change of draught through the buoy motion and wave elevation. The forces are treated as unidirectional and can therefore be combined easily. Since the geometry of the buoys and therefore the cross-sectional area changes, table 2.4 shows the maximum possible wind and current force for each buoy type (the minimum is 0 N).

The drag coefficients are $C_{WW} = 0.35$ for the wind and $C_{WC} = 1.2$ for the current (Spektrum 1998). The fluid density for water was assumed as $\rho_W = 1025 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ and $\rho_A = 1.204 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ for air.

As mentioned in section 2.2.2, the expected 50-year wind speed from $z_1 = 61$ m will be corrected to $z_2 = 3$ m above the SWL in accordance to DNV AS (2019) with $z_0 = 0.005$ m.

$$v_3 = v_{61} \cdot \frac{\ln \frac{z_2}{z_0}}{\ln \frac{z_1}{z_0}} \quad (2.20)$$

This leads to the force values seen in table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Maximum possible wind and current forces for all buoy types.

Buoy	Wind Force	Current Force
Buoy 1	107.4 N	837.4 N
Buoy 2	88.6 N	644.6 N
Buoy 3	166.3 N	1332.6 N
Buoy 4	67.8 N	535.9 N

2.3.3 Line Force

As stated, the mooring line is treated as a steel cable that acts as a spring which does not absorb bending or torsion moments and compression forces. Therefore, the line force is only present while the distance $s = \sqrt{x^2 + (b - z)^2}$ between buoy and attachment point on the tube exceeds the set line length of, $b = 7m$ so that $\Delta s = s - b$. Figure 2.16 shows a sketch of this relation. The x and z values are the position coordinates of the buoy in the x-z plane.

$$F_{Line} = c_l \cdot \Delta s \quad \text{for} \quad s \geq b \quad (2.21)$$

where the spring constant c_l of the line is

$$c_l = E \cdot \frac{A_l}{b} \quad (2.22)$$

with the Young's module $E = 1.13 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}^2}$ of the steel cable and $A_l = 0.455 \cdot \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$ the equivalent cross-section of the steel cable (Orcina n.d.). With a diameter of 20 mm the spring constant therefore equates to $c_l \approx 2.3 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}}$.

Figure 2.16: Diagram of the buoy system with the still water line, the line length s , the anchor depth $b = 7$ m, the x and z coordinates of the buoy and the resulting angle α between buoy line and horizontal plane.

The line force is split into an x and a z component.

$$F_{Line_x} = F_{Line} \cdot \cos \alpha \quad (2.23)$$

$$F_{Line_z} = F_{Line} \cdot \sin \alpha \quad (2.24)$$

Because of this, there is always a restoring force in the correct direction should the buoy move further than b away from the anchor point.

3 Calculation

To calculate the buoys' response to the environment, a dynamic time domain solution will be employed. In contrast to a static approach, where the loads are applied to a body in a fixed position, in the dynamic approach the body is free to move which makes it possible to predict and calculate possible resonance effects. This method is needed since the acting forces are not all linear, and therefore the superposition principle does not apply (Journée and Massie 2001). It also enables the possibility to account for so-called snap loads that are often critical for the loads on the system (Niedzwecki and Thampi 1991).

For a time domain solution, firstly a time dependent wave elevation η has to be extracted from the wave spectra introduced in chapter 2.2.3 (Journée and Massie 2001). This is achieved through the addition of a discrete number of equally spaced frequencies N from the wave spectrum with a random phase shift (Holthuijsen 2007). In this thesis $N = 1000$ was chosen to get a wide spectrum while keeping the calculation effort reasonably low.

$$\eta = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \cdot \cos(2\pi f_i + \alpha_i) \quad (3.1)$$

where α_i is a uniformly distributed random phase shift between 0 and 2π .

$$p(\alpha_i) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \quad \text{for } 0 < \alpha_i \leq 2\pi \quad (3.2)$$

This results in an irregular series of wave surface height that is different in almost every iteration.

Figure 3.1: Summation of many harmonic waves with constant amplitude and random phase from within the frequency spectrum add up to one irregular sea surface description from Holthuijsen (2007).

This allows the transfer from frequency domain to time domain (Journée and Massie 2001).

3.1 Equation of Motion

For the buoy position, velocity and acceleration, Newton's second law is employed

$$\frac{F}{m} = \dot{c} \quad (3.3)$$

where in turn velocity and position can be integrated from.

Since the buoy is modelled in two dimensions (x, z), the forces in chapter 2.3 must be added up to a resulting force in x and z direction respectively.

$$F_x = F_{Line_x} + F_{Morison} + F_W + F_C \quad (3.4)$$

$$F_z = F_{Line_z} + F_H + F_{Wavev} \quad (3.5)$$

With equation 3.3 and a buoy mass m , equations 3.4 and 3.5 then result in an acceleration $\dot{c}_z = \ddot{z}$ and $\dot{c}_x = \ddot{x}$.

3.2 Numerical Approach

Since the solution for the buoy behaviour will be calculated in the time domain and since the forces are dependent on buoy position, wave elevation, buoy velocity and acceleration, an analytical solution of the equation of motion is not possible. Because of this, a numerical

approach has to be employed (Dhanak and Xiros 2016).

Numerical solutions act through dividing the timeframe of calculation into a number of single time steps and connect these with individual lines (Munz and Westermann 2019). With an appropriate amount of time steps, the real solution can then be approximated satisfactorily. The simplest of these numerical methods is the so called explicit Euler-Cauchy method which is displayed in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: The explicit Euler method of integration with an exact result for comparison: (a) Single step and (b) Multiple steps from Mostoufi and Constantinides (2023).

The points are connected with a single straight line with the equation

$$y_{i+1} = y_i + \Delta t \cdot f(x_i, y_i) \quad (3.6)$$

where $\Delta t = x_2 - x_1$ is the stepsize. Applied to the terminology within this thesis and equation 3.3 this becomes

$$\dot{x}_{i+1} = \dot{x}_i + \Delta t \cdot \frac{F_{x_i}}{m} \quad (3.7)$$

and

$$\dot{z}_{i+1} = \dot{z}_i + \Delta t \cdot \frac{F_{z_i}}{m} \quad (3.8)$$

Since the explicit Euler Method calculates the speed during the next time step (\dot{z}_{i+1}) with the force of the current one (F_{z_i}) it is prone to error in stiff problems such as the equation of the buoy motion (Butcher 2003). Therefore, a variation of the Euler method will be used, the implicit Euler method.

$$\dot{z}_{i+1} = \dot{z}_i + \Delta t \cdot \frac{F_{z_{i+1}}}{m} \quad (3.9)$$

With this method, the speed at time step i is calculated from the force at time step i which leads to higher system stability (Butcher 2003). This however leads to an equation that cannot be solved as easily as before, since now the force calculation requires, \dot{z}_{i+1} which in turn relies on the resulting force. The resulting equations have therefore to be solved with

another method for each time step in order to get a result. This is done with the root finding algorithm "fsolve" in python. This method provides stable results at the cost of much higher needed computational resources.

After solving for the buoys' velocity, the position and acceleration can be approximated as well.

$$z_{i+1} = z_i + \dot{z}_{i+1} \cdot \Delta t \quad (3.10)$$

and

$$\ddot{z}_{i+1} = \frac{\dot{z}_{i+1} - \dot{z}_i}{\Delta t} \quad (3.11)$$

This now also enables the update of other related values such as the drought, which changes from a baseline value θ_0 when the system is at rest, to a dynamic value

$$\theta_i = \theta_0 + \eta_i - z_i \quad (3.12)$$

which directly translates into displaced water volume V and cross-sectional area A above and below water. With these values saved, the calculation advances one time step and the procedure is repeated until the defined timeframe is reached.

3.3 Numerical Challenges

As mentioned above, the driving problem of numerical solutions is their stability, or lack thereof. If the systems' equations are stable in their energy conservation, the instability can still arise from a lack of sample steps. Especially in stiff and quickly changing systems, such as the line force, a time step size that is too large might introduce instability. This inherently makes sense, when considering a body hitting a wall. Intuitively, one expects the body to bounce off after reaching the wall, however in a calculation with a limited size of time steps this is not completely true. The larger the time step, the further the body can "travel" into the wall without a repulsing force acting on it. This is shown schematically in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Example of a body hitting a wall with differently sized time steps. In the left figure the time resolution is much lower allowing the body to travel into the wall further.

If we now imagine this repulsion force being relative to the depth of intrusion of the body below the line. A body, calculated with fewer time steps, may experience forces exceeding what energy conservation permits. In an oscillating system, this could now lead to an ever-increasing growth in force, where the body flies higher with every bounce.

The second problem with numerical solutions is the computational time it takes to get results. This is closely related to the amount of time steps and the complexity of equations solved during every step (e.g. implicit equations). Generally computational time exceeds the calculated time series which makes it difficult to calculate larger time frames, or many repetitions of shorter ones (Journée and Massie 2001).

4 Results and Evaluation

In this chapter, the calculation results for the buoy movements and line forces are shown. The chapter starts with detailed results for one example buoy. Afterwards, the results for all the buoys will be shown in a comparative fashion.

To simulate a full storm, buoy movement was calculated over a 3-hour period.

4.1 Example: Buoy 4

In order to keep this section as concise as possible, Buoy 4 is used as an arbitrary example for the detailed calculation results. In addition, the result graphs for all buoys can be found in Appendix B.

4.1.1 Sea State 1

The following graphs show the horizontal and vertical position changes in addition to the mooring line forces for the sea state 1 with $H_s = 3.9$ m and $T_p = 5.9$ s.

Figure 4.1: Numerically calculated position of buoy 4 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

For sea state 1 it is notable, that the horizontal x movement does not oscillate around 0 but instead around about 0.85 m. The reason for this is that although the horizontal wave force has a mean of zero (within the uncertainties of an irregular sea state) the wind and current forces are always positive. This suggests that the wave forces on average lie below the wind and current force. In the z position, this is portrayed in a lack of 0 crossings.

Figure 4.2: Numerically calculated line force through the buoy 4 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours.

As mentioned above, the wind and current forces seem to be constantly bigger than the horizontal wave forces. This can be seen in figure 4.2 as well because the line forces do not reach 0 since the line is constantly under tension from the wind and current.

The largest calculated line force for this sea state and buoy combination was approximately 1370 N.

4.1.2 Sea State 2

The following graphs show the horizontal and vertical position changes in addition to the mooring line forces for the sea state 2 with $H_s = 3.9$ m and $T_p = 13.7$ s.

Figure 4.3: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure 4.3 a): Enlarged section of figure 4.3 to show the two overlaying plots better.

In comparison to figure 4.1 of sea state 1 in sea state 2, zero crossings for the x are shown. However, the influence of the wind and current forces are still clearly visible, as the median is shifted to a positive value. Since negative values for x are possible, this means that the

horizontal wave forces are not always smaller than the wind and current forces. This is also portrayed in the z position, because a full surfacing of the buoy ($z = 0$) is visible, which is only possible with a horizontal force that is near 0.

Figure 4.4: Numerically calculated line force through buoy movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

For the line forces it is noteworthy, that the forces now reach 0 frequently, which implies a slack mooring line. Additionally, it is interesting that the maximum loads are up to two orders of magnitude higher than the bulk of the forces and only appear rarely. This shows that in a simulation of an irregular sea, particularly unfavourable circumstances can appear simultaneously. This can result in an unexpected force spike, although the average force is significantly lower. The maximum calculated line force was approximately 30 000 N

4.1.3 Sea State 3

The following graphs show the horizontal and vertical position changes in addition to the mooring line forces for the sea state 3 with $H_s = 7.8$ m and $T_p = 15.7$ s.

Figure 4.5: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. Lines are drawn at the original line length of ± 7 m and at twice that value in the negative direction -14 m to show the maximum possible buoy movements without line elongation.

Figure 4.5 a): Enlarged section of figure 4.5 to show the two overlapping plots better.

In contrast to sea state 1 and 2 in sea state 3 the influence of the wind and current loads are not as easily visible any more. This shows that the sea state 3 contains the highest wave

force of the three sea states.

As can be seen in figure 4.5 there is a clear plateau or limit for the x and z position visible. For the x position this is about ± 7 m and for the z position it is 0 m and -14 m. These values stem from the line length of, $b = 7$ m and are therefore the maximum possible values the buoy could achieve without stretching the line as shown in figure 4.6. For, $x = 7$ m this represents a buoy position where the mooring line is in a horizontal position and the buoy is 7 m below the mean water line, at the depth of the anchor point. For, $z = -14$ m the mooring line is vertical and stretches another 7 m downwards from the anchor point before it reaches the buoy position.

Figure 4.6: The figure shows the still water line and the maximum positions the buoys can reach in the model without stretching the line. These Positions are at $(0|0)$, $(7|0)$, $(-7|0)$ and $(0|-14)$.

One can imagine that a position with the buoy at $z=-14$ m is only easily possible within the simplification of this model, not with an actual structure present and in the way. However, in such a storm one might also question the assumption of a fixed anchor point which could also be changing position with the whole of the system.

Figure 4.7: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Since sea state 3 contains the highest wave force as mentioned above, it also exerts the highest amount of force on the mooring lines. With a maximum of approximately, 320 000 N the exerted forces are, in most cases, over one hundred times bigger than during sea state 1 (see section 4.2 for why the force peak of $F > 350\,000$ N at $t = 1$ s will be excluded). Because of this, it is of especially great interest for the buoy design and is to be especially critically evaluated.

Since the result for sea state 3 are rather extreme in their behaviour, their interpretation is more prone to bias, and some model testing would be especially advisable here to eliminate this.

4.1.4 Line Tension and Force

As mentioned in Chapter 3, snap loads are suspected to introduce the highest forces to the system. In order to investigate the influence of the snap loads on the line forces, the forces are plotted over the change in distance to the anchor point. A negative value in Δs means that the buoy is closer to the anchor point than, the original line length $b = 7$ m and that the line is therefore slack.

Figure 4.8: Example of numerically calculated line forces and corresponding values of change in distance to the anchor point compared to the resting body position Δs over a 100-second period. Negative Δs values correspond to a slack line, positive or zero values to a taut line.

To make that relation more easily visible, the next two graphs 4.9 and 4.10 show an enlarged detail.

Figure 4.9: Enlarged detail 1 of figure 4.8 showing numerically calculated line forces and corresponding values of change in distance to the anchor point compared to the resting body position Δs over a 100-second period. Negative Δs values correspond to a slack line, positive or zero values to a taut line.

As can be seen in figures 4.8 and 4.9 the highest peaks in force are preceded by a slack mooring line that allows the buoy free movement. This indicates that in fact the snap loads are the predominant factor in line force, although figure 4.10 below shows that spikes in the line force can also arise from a taut line. These spikes are, however, much smaller than the ones mentioned before.

Figure 4.10: Enlarged detail 2 of figure 4.8 showing numerically calculated line forces and corresponding values of change in distance to the anchor point compared to the resting body position Δs over a 100-second period. Negative Δs values correspond to a slack line, positive or zero values to a taut line.

In order to combat the appearance of snap loads, the employment of a higher pretension load for the mooring lines should be considered. This would raise the base load on the mooring line while limiting the likely-hood of snap loads through sustaining a taut mooring line.

4.2 Buoy Comparison

In this section, the calculated forces of the four different buoys will be shown. For the maximum forces, the peaks at the simulation beginnings will not be considered because they are unreasonably large. This is because they stem from the instantaneous forces on the fully resting system. This behaviour is only based on the calculation setup and not grounded in reality.

The maximum values for all sea states for all buoys are shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Maximum line forces for all buoys across the different sea states.

Buoy	Sea State 1	Sea State 2	Sea State 3
Buoy 1	1946 N	3150 N	330 000 N
Buoy 2	2490 N	71 000 N	390 000 N
Buoy 3	10 100 N	159 000 N	850 000 N
Buoy 4	1370 N	30 000 N	320 000 N

For easier comparison, the values are plotted in a bar chart in figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11: Maximum line forces for the four different buoy types that were calculated in all three sea states (sea state 1: $H_s = 3.9\text{ m}/T_p = 5.9\text{ s}$, sea state 2: $H_s = 3.9\text{ m}/T_p = 13.7\text{ s}$, sea state 3: $H_s = 7.8\text{ m}/T_p = 15.7\text{ s}$). Note that the scale of the y-axis is logarithmic.

In the calculations, Buoy 3 exerted the maximum force on the mooring line over all three sea states. Especially in figure 4.12, showing sea state 1 where the lowest forces were calculated for all the buoys, this is visible.

Figure 4.12: Maximum line forces for the four different buoy types that were calculated for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9\text{ m}/T_p = 5.9\text{ s}$).

The forces from Buoy 3 are almost a full order of magnitude bigger than the ones of its competitors.

In order to better compare the buoys, the force per liter buoyancy is calculated in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Maximum line forces per liter of buoyancy for all buoys across the different sea states.

Buoy	Sea State 1	Sea State 2	Sea State 3
Buoy 1	9.73 N	15.75 N	1650 N
Buoy 2	11.97 N	341.35 N	1875 N
Buoy 3	18.04 N	283.93 N	1517.86 N
Buoy 4	12.57 N	275.23 N	2935.78 N

Again, the results are plotted in figure 4.13 for comparison.

Figure 4.13: Maximum line forces per liter buoyancy for the four different buoy types that were calculated in all three sea states (sea state 1: $H_s = 3.9 \text{ m}/T_p = 5.9 \text{ s}$, sea state 2: $H_s = 3.9 \text{ m}/T_p = 13.7 \text{ s}$, sea state 3: $H_s = 7.8 \text{ m}/T_p = 15.7 \text{ s}$). Note that the scale of the y-axis is logarithmic.

4.3 Interpretation of Maximum Buoy Forces

This section aims to give guidance on the comparison of the buoys from their calculated maximum forces.

Between the three different sea states, sea state 3 produced the highest forces for all four buoys, and even the smallest maximum force in sea state 3 is twice as big as the biggest maximum in sea state 2. This was generally to be expected, since the third sea state has the highest significant wave height and therefore the most energy in the wave spectrum. Because the forces are so significant, the values of sea state 3 are the ones that will be used to compare the buoys regarding their maximum force. Here it is noted, that the sea state 2 also produces bigger forces on the mooring line than the sea state 1 while being identical in significant wave height H_s . The difference in energy stems from the increase in peak wave period T_p . However, this relation of wave energy to line force is also governed by the ability of the waves to impart that energy into the buoy. For example, a differently sized buoy might react differently to the wave spectra.

As can be seen in table 4.1 the maximum calculated forces for sea state 3 come from Buoy

3 with 850 000 N and the lowest from Buoy 1 with 330 000 N. However, Buoy 3 is also the biggest in volume and mass of the four different buoys, with it being more than five times the buoyancy of for example Buoy 4 with just 109 l. Because of this, higher forces, were therefore to be expected. As stated above, a force per liter was calculated to eliminate this difference and to make for another way of comparison.

Per liter buoyancy the ranking shifts and Buoy 4 has now the maximum force while Buoy 3 (that exerts the maximum force over all) now has the lowest value with $1517.86 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{l}}$. This results in the fact that Buoy 3 might be the best or the worst option, depending on the surrounding design constraints. Buoy 1 might also be a good pick since as mentioned it is best in class for maximum force and only slightly behind first place for the force per buoyancy.

5 Summary and Conclusion

This bachelor thesis aimed to calculate and compare the mooring forces acting on a single point moored buoy in the German North Sea. This involved the development of a simplified model for the system and specifically the buoys. Afterwards, statistical evaluation of the site specific environmental data in order to predict realistic environmental influences was performed and the equations for transferring the environmental behaviour into forces acting on the buoy were defined. Lastly, the dynamic behaviour of the buoys under the defined forces was numerically calculated through python.

The results for the maximum mooring line forces were compared and the best performing buoy over all was the Buoy 1 and the worst performing the Buoy 3. However, for the force per liter buoyancy, the Buoy 3 performed best and the Buoy 4 performed worst. The overall forces varied widely between the three different sea states. With sea state 3 introducing forces that are up to 100 times bigger than the forces in sea state 1 this highlights the need for a reliable prediction of the environment and the need to take more extreme events into account when designing offshore systems. The gained results also highlight the advantages of a dynamic calculation to predict snap loads, which improves awareness for their influence.

The results obtained in this thesis can improve prediction of the buoy design requirements around the location of the FINO3 and serve as a foundation for similar projects in the future. The calculation results can be used to predict needed design requirements and can therefore help minimize failure, which in turn increases the safety, reduces costs and limits the environmental impact.

In order to verify the results obtained, comparison with other works such as Sjøkvist et al. (2017) and Rykkje, Tørressen, and Løkkebø (2019) was performed. The comparison produced similar results, which strengthen the reliability of this thesis. However, this allows only for a rough validation, since the buoys and the mooring arrangement analysed in the two sources quite differ from the mussel system.

Despite the usefulness of the results, the limitations of the modelling approach should be acknowledged. The main model simplifications were the assumption of a fixed anchor point

to reduce the complexity to a single body problem and the lack of detailed information about the buoy coefficients. Additionally, the two-dimensionality and neglect of possible buoy rotation simplified the buoy movement. The environmental behaviour was simplified with the assumption of unidirectionality, lack of a wind gust spectrum and the limited complexity of the wave and wave-structure interaction models such as particle motion, vortex shedding and a change in wave force over water depth. Lastly, the simulation time and number of runs were limited by the computational resources, which might have led to the possible oversight of higher load combinations. It should be noted, that the forces for sea state 3 are not unlikely to surpass the breaking strength of a common 20mm steel wire. Because of this, the calculations could be repeated with a thicker wire. Since changing the wire diameter also changes the spring constant, this change in turn might have influence on the dynamic behaviour of the system and therefore on the expected forces. An improvement in any of these fields might improve results in the future.

Since the python scripts used for this thesis will be handed over to the FuE-Zentrum FH Kiel GmbH, there are many easy opportunities for refinement and adaptations in the future, to which this thesis can be seen as a groundwork.

Possible refinements could include more detailed buoy coefficients obtained through model testing or the use of additional environmental data over a longer time frame for a more reliable statistical analysis.

Adaptation could be possible, for example for different buoys, different mooring lines, increased pretension, varying mooring depths and overall aquaculture system configuration. In addition, the environmental requirements could be changed, for example with different return periods (e.g. 100-year wind speed) or for a differing location (e.g. Dutch North Sea) although it should be noted, that a change in location might diminish the applicability of for example the JONSWAP spectrum. Any increase in complexity might also come with an increase in the need for computational resources, which should be kept in mind.

This thesis has highlighted the steps necessary to calculate the mooring forces on a buoy in the German North Sea, showing possible procedures and obstacles along the way. Together with providing actual exemplary results for all the calculations, the insights gained will contribute to the further development of safer and more reliable designs for the offshore industry.

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A Environmental Factors

Additional figures regarding the environmental analysis.

Figure A.1: Wind speed extreme value selection using a $8.83 \frac{m}{s}$ threshold and a 24-hour cluster size. The wind speed data are INSITU measurements taken at the FINO3 research platform between October 2012 and September 2023.

Figure A.2: Current speed extreme value selection using a $0.426 \frac{m}{s}$ threshold and a 24-hour cluster size. The current speed data are INSITU measurements taken at the FINO3 research platform between October 2012 and September 2023.

Figure A.3: Environmental contour plot for a return period of 50-years, drawn with the python module "virocon". All hypothetical data pairs that lay on the contour line have the same occurrence probability of 2% per year.

Figure A.4: Number of wind speed data points per month of the year. The data points are INSITU wind speed measurements taken every ten minutes at the research platform FINO3 between 01.10.2013 until 30.09.2023.

Figure A.5: Number of current speed data points per month of the year. The data points are INSITU current speed measurements taken every ten minutes at the research platform FINO3 between 01.10.2013 until 30.09.2023.

Figure A.6: Number of wave height data points per month of the year. The data points are INSITU wave height measurements taken every ten minutes at the research platform FINO3 between 01.10.2013 until 30.09.2023.

B Calculation Results

All figures produced through the buoy movement calculation for all sea states and buoys.

B.1 Buoy 1

B.1.1 Sea State 1

Figure B.1: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.2: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.3: Detailed view of figure B.2, the numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.4: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.5: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The peak at $t = 1$ s is considered a simulation artefact.

Figure B.6: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.7: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.6 around the peak value.

B.1.2 Sea State 2

Figure B.8: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.9: Detailed view of figure B.8. Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.10: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The peak at $t = 1$ s is considered a simulation artefact.

Figure B.11: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.10 around the peak value.

B.1.3 Sea State 3

Figure B.12: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.13: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. Detailed view of figure B.12.

Figure B.14: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.15: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.14 around the peak value.

Figure B.16: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 1 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a further enlarged detailed view of figure B.14 around the peak value.

B.2 Buoy 2

B.2.1 Sea State 1

Figure B.17: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 2 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.18: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 2 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.19: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The peak at $t = 1$ s is considered a simulation artefact.

Figure B.20: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.21: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.20 around the peak value.

B.2.2 Sea State 2

Figure B.22: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 2 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.23: Detailed view of figure B.22. Numerically calculated position of Buoy 2 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9\text{ m}$, $T_p = 13.7\text{ s}$) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.24: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9\text{ m}$, $T_p = 13.7\text{ s}$) over a time of three hours. The peak at $t = 1\text{ s}$ is considered a simulation artefact.

Figure B.25: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.24 around the peak value.

Figure B.26: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.24 around the peak value.

B.2.3 Sea State 3

Figure B.27: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 2 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.28: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 1 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. Detailed view of figure B.27.

Figure B.29: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.30: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.29 around the peak value.

Figure B.31: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 2 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a further enlarged detailed view of figure B.29 around the peak value.

B.3 Buoy 3

B.3.1 Sea State 1

Figure B.32: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.33: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.34: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The peak at $t = 1$ s is considered a simulation artefact.

Figure B.35: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.36: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.35 around the peak value.

B.3.2 Sea State 2

Figure B.37: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.38: Detailed view of figure B.37. Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.39: Detailed view of figure B.37. Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. This figure highlights the difference in oscillation frequency between x and z coordinate.

Figure B.40: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.41: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.40 around the peak value.

Figure B.42: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.40 around the peak value.

B.3.3 Sea State 3

Figure B.43: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.44: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 3 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. Detailed view of figure B.43.

Figure B.45: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.46: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.45 around the peak value.

Figure B.47: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 3 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.45 around the peak value.

B.4 Buoy 4

B.4.1 Sea State 1

Figure B.48: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.49: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in x direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.50: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) in z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.51: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The peak at $t = 1$ s is considered a simulation artefact.

Figure B.52: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.53: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 1 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 5.9$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.6 around the peak value.

B.4.2 Sea State 2

Figure B.54: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.55: Detailed view of figure B.8. Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.56: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.57: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9$ m, $T_p = 13.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.56 around the peak value.

Figure B.58: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 2 ($H_s = 3.9\text{ m}$, $T_p = 13.7\text{ s}$) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.56 around the peak value.

B.4.3 Sea State 3

Figure B.59: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8\text{ m}$, $T_p = 15.7\text{ s}$) in x and z direction over a time of three hours.

Figure B.60: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. Detailed view of figure B.59.

Figure B.61: Numerically calculated position of Buoy 4 for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) in x and z direction over a time of three hours. Detailed view of figure B.59.

Figure B.62: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours.

Figure B.63: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.62 around the peak value.

Figure B.64: Numerically calculated line force through the Buoy 4 movement for sea state 3 ($H_s = 7.8$ m, $T_p = 15.7$ s) over a time of three hours. The displayed area is a detailed view of figure B.62 around the peak value.

Erklärung der Urheberschaft/ Declaration of Authorship

Ich versichere, dass ich die Bachelorarbeit "Calculation and comparison of mooring forces on a single point moored buoy in an aquaculture system located in the German North Sea" selbständig und ohne unzulässige fremde Hilfe angefertigt habe und dass ich alle von anderen Autoren wörtlich übernommenen Stellen wie auch die sich an die Gedankengänge anderer Autoren eng anlehrenden Ausführungen meiner Arbeit besonders gekennzeichnet und die entsprechenden Quellen angegeben habe.

Diese Arbeit hat noch keiner Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegen.

Kiel, 27.01.2025

Jan Sykora